

AN INVESTIGATION ON THE SOIL AND PEAT HUMIC ACIDS. PART II. OXIDATION WITH HYDROGEN PEROXIDE, HOT ALKALI AND CHLORINE DIOXIDE SOLUTION.

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A humic acid from peat and another from an Assam tea soil were oxidised by various strengths of H_2O_2 both as pure acid and as the Ca salt. They were also subjected to a method of degradation similar to that used by Freudenberg in connection with lignin. Products of the same nature were isolated. The acids were also oxidised by ClO_2 and oxalic and butyric acids detected in the products.

König (*Landow. jahrb.*, 1920, 56, 185), Robinson (*J. Agric. Res.*, 1927, 34, 339), Springer (*Z. Pflanz. Dung. Bod.*, 1928, A11, 313), Waksman (*Soil Sci.*, 1930, 30, 97) and others have treated soils with varying concentrations of hydrogen peroxide to determine the humus content as they believed that the organic portion of the soil was more or less completely oxidised by this reagent to carbon dioxide and water. König found besides carbon dioxide, acetic and formic acids in the solution. Wheeler (*J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1927, 5, 849) also concluded that certain aliphatic carboxylic acids, especially oxalic and succinic, as well as aromatic polycarboxy acids may be formed during this reaction. Attempts have been made in the present investigation to ascertain the nature of the intermediary substances, if any, formed in the oxidation of humic acid by hydrogen peroxide.

EXPERIMENTAL.

About 0.5 g. of commercial peat humic acid was dissolved in 20 c. c. of 3% caustic soda solution and hydrogen peroxide solution (50 c. c., 15%) was added at the ordinary temperature dropwise from a dropping funnel with constant stirring. Vigorous frothing accompanied the reaction. The reaction was allowed to proceed overnight. Next day the excess of hydrogen peroxide was decomposed by heating on the water-bath. The solution was then made just acid by means of hydrochloric acid and the precipitate filtered off. This precipitate was washed and analysed after conversion into barium salt. The filtrate was extracted with ethyl acetate thrice and the solvent evaporated. The acid mother-liquor left after removal of acetic acid in *vacuo* over caustic potash, was converted into a barium salt from which barium was estimated. The ethyl acetate extract on evaporation in *vacuo* gave a brownish red, gummy substance. It had a perceptible characteristic odour, like that of pyruvic acid. It gave

an instantaneous frothing in contact with a solution of sodium bicarbonate and with ferric chloride gave a violet colouration indicating its phenolic character. It also reduced an ammoniacal silver nitrate solution when heated. It also formed well defined insoluble salts of copper, lead and silver. Barium and calcium salts were formed only when the solutions were heated and kept for some time.

Attempts were made to fractionate the ethyl acetate extract. The substance is insoluble in benzene, but the major part dissolves in ether, giving a brownish solution and leaving a greyish white powdery substance. The ether-soluble portion was found to be more acidic. The two portions were separately analysed for carbon, nitrogen etc. The ether-soluble portion gave all the tests previously described more prominently. No nitrogen was found in this portion (Found: C, 44.58; H, 5.6 per cent). The substance was found to be extremely hygroscopic. The ether-insoluble portion was of a greyish white colour and was not so hygroscopic as the soluble fraction. This also gave all the previous tests. The amount was too small for analysis. The exact nature of these acids could not be cleared up. Moreover, a trace of a gummy brown substance associated with the acid could not be successfully removed. That they were phenolic or aldehydic carboxylic acids was indicated by their properties. The first fraction that separated out after treating the oxidised solution with hydrochloric acid was dissolved in ammonia and sufficient barium chloride added. The precipitated barium salt was filtered, completely washed, dried at 105° and analysed for barium. The ethyl acetate extract and the mother-liquor were analysed in the same way.

In other experiments, hydrogen peroxide of different amounts were used. In one case, the oxidised humic acid was re-oxidised with the same agent to see whether a further degradation was possible. The Ba salts in the various fractions were found to contain varied amount of barium in different preparations. Even a dilute solution of hydrogen peroxide can oxidise the humic acid molecule, but the degree of oxidation varies with the concentration of hydrogen peroxide used, the temperature, the amount of alkali present and the time given for the reaction. The optimum temperature was found to be 30-40°, the concentration of hydrogen peroxide to be 12-15% and that of the alkali 2-3%. With the increase in the amount of hydrogen peroxide added, the equivalent weight of the resulting products decreased as is seen from the increasing percentage of barium in their barium salts (*vide* Table I). It has been reported that the oxidation of humus is facilitated in the presence of lime. To test this view the following experiment was carried out.

Oxidation of the Ca salt of the Humic Acid by Hydrogen Peroxide.

Humic acid (10 g.) was dissolved in ammonia and sufficient calcium chloride solution added. The calcium humate formed was filtered off after complete washing with water, suspended in water without drying, and hydrogen peroxide was added very slowly drop by drop. The reaction was very slow at the ordinary temperature. The temperature of the mixture was gradually raised to 75°. It was found that the most convenient temperature was 70-80°. After complete reaction, i.e. when the effervescence ceased, the original calcium humate changed to a greyish white powder and this was separated from the greenish yellow filtrate by filtration and washing. The filtrate was found to be acidic. The acid filtrate on treatment with ethyl acetate gave no appreciable extract.

The white powdery mass left after oxidation of the grey calcium humate was dissolved in hydrochloric acid and the clear yellowish solution after filtration was extracted with ethyl acetate and the extract on evaporation gave a greyish white powder. This was sparingly soluble in water but dissolved in ammonia and gave a strong effervescence with a solution of sodium bicarbonate indicating its acid nature. It gave no appreciable colouration with ferric chloride. It was suspected that the acid residue was a mixture. When heated in a platinum foil a very small amount of ash was left. The ethyl acetate fraction on analysis gave C, 56.20; H, 6.4 per cent.

TABLE I.

Oxidation of calcium humate by H₂O₂.

Ca salt.	15% H ₂ O ₂ .	Ca in the oxidised salt.	Equiv. calc. from % Ca.
5 g.	75 c.c.	15.57%	109.45
1	20	17.35	96.25
2	50	17.79	93.45
1	30	22.62	69.9

TABLE II.

Equivalent wts. from the barium salts in the several extracts.

Humic acid.	3% KOH soln.	15% H ₂ O ₂ .	Ethyl acetate extract.	1st acid ppt.	Mother-liquor after ethyl acetate extraction.
5 g.	80 c.c.	120 c.c.	116	116	103
1	40	30	116	104	96
3	60	120	115	102	92
0.5	20	50	114	100	93

The soil humic acid was treated with hydrogen peroxide in the same way. The ethyl acetate extract in this case also showed similar phenolic and acidic properties.

Potash-fusion followed by Methylation and Permanganate Oxidation.—By mild fusion with caustic potash followed by alkaline permanganate oxidation of lignin, Freudenberg and others (*Ber.*, 1937, 70, 500) have isolated veratric, veratroylformic and isobemipinic acids and thus gave an insight into the molecular structure of lignin. The aromatic character of lignin has been amply verified. To test the correctness of this lignin hypothesis of the origin of humic acid, the following treatment was carried out. The products identical with those obtained by Freudenberg from lignin have been isolated.

Humic acid (10 g.) was suspended in water (40 c.c.) and caustic potash (90 g.) was added and the mixture was refluxed at 170°. In ½ hour the frothing started. All this time the flask was vigorously shaken. After 1½ hours the mixture was cooled to 130° and poured into 200 c.c. of water resulting in a dark brown solution. When the temperature came down to 60-70°, 140 c.c. of dimethyl sulphate was added drop by drop and the mixture kept vigorously agitated till it became acid to congo red. The methylated product that separated out, was filtered, washed with hot water thrice and dried at 100°. The filtrate was subjected to steam distillation, but no volatile organic acid was precisely detected in the distillate. The yield of the methylated product was about 8.5 g. This treatment with alkali and methylation by dimethyl sulphate was repeated till the methylation was supposed to be complete. The methylated acid was dissolved in acetone and poured into a litre of water at the room temperature, when a fine brown precipitate was thrown down, through which air was passed at 95° to remove acetone. This process gave the methylated acid in a fine state of division. It was then cooled to 60° and the liquid was treated with finely powdered potassium permanganate in portions of 3 g. with vigorous stirring. The temperature was gradually allowed to rise on a water-bath to 95° and potassium permanganate was added. After 4-5 additions the solution was cooled, nearly neutralised with 3*N*-sulphuric acid. The temperature was again raised to 95° and about 40 g. of more potassium permanganate were added in portions of 3 g. in the course of ½ hour. The manganese dioxide was filtered off and washed with water, and dissolved in sulphurous acid. After filtering off a small black residue the filtrate was extracted thrice with ether.

The slightly yellow alkaline filtrate from manganese dioxide was

just acidified to litmus with 2*N*-sulphuric acid and extracted with ether. The ethereal solution was dried with sodium sulphate and evaporated. The residue left was a brownish gum and smelt like the lower fatty acids. This substance was fractionated further (X). The solution left after ether extraction was acidified to congo red, saturated with ammonium sulphate and then extracted with ethyl acetate. Fine colourless needles separated out when the ethyl acetate extract was concentrated to a small bulk and cooled to 0°. The colourless crystals (A) separated on centrifuging and the extract was allowed to evaporate. The yellow-brown residue left was treated with hot benzene. This on cooling gave a white powder (B) which was separated by centrifuging and the cooled benzene solution on evaporation, left a gummy substance. The residue that was insoluble in hot benzene was dissolved in acetone and a slight fine white precipitate that appeared was separated by centrifuging (C). The mother-liquor after concentrating to a smaller bulk was treated with a few drops of acetonitrile and centrifuged when a white gummy substance separated out (D).

Treatment of the Ether Extract (X).—The residue left after evaporating the ethereal solution was treated with hot benzene. The benzene extract on evaporation gave a greyish waxy substance with a peculiar odour which was insoluble in water. This was neglected. The residue insoluble in hot benzene was dissolved in acetone, concentrated to a small bulk and treated with a few drops of acetonitrile, when fine colourless crystals appeared, which were separated by a centrifuge, and were dried in a vacuum desiccator. It is insoluble in water and when heated in a sealed tube it partly sublimes and partly decomposes at 250° characteristic of isohemipinic acid (m.p. 249°).

Treatment of Fraction "A" of the Ethyl Acetate Extract.—The needle-like crystals separating from the cold concentrated ethyl acetate extract were again dissolved in hot benzene. The benzene solution on concentration gave fine white crystals. These crystals were insoluble in cold water but dissolved in sufficient hot water. On cooling fine crystals appeared which were centrifuged and dried in a vacuum desiccator, m.p. 178° (mixed m.p. with an authentic specimen of veratric acid).

Treatment of the Fraction (B).—The white crystals from (B) obtained on cooling the hot benzene solution of the ethyl acetate extract were separated by a centrifuge. On recrystallisation from water white crystals of veratric acid came out. The mother-liquor on treatment with charcoal and concentration gave a light yellow substance, m.p. 143°. This is possibly a mixture of veratric and veratroylformic acid.

Treatment of the Fractions (C) and (D).—The white gummy subs-

tance obtained after centrifuging the acetone extract was dried in a vacuum desiccator. It was acidic and probably the high molecular acid described by Freudenberg. The clear reddish brown acetone mixture was treated with freshly heated animal charcoal whereby the red colour slightly diminished. The solution after centrifuging was treated with a few drops of acetonitrile, when a gum-like white substance separated. This was acidic and might be impure isohemipinic acid.

Oxidation of the Soil Humic Acid.—The process of potash-fusion, methylation and oxidation was repeated in case of soil humic acid also, but some difference was marked in this case. The alkaline solution after oxidation was found more yellowish. When this solution was acidified with 2*N*-sulphuric acid to congo red, a white amorphous mass separated out. This white mass (A) was filtered off. The acidified filtrate was first treated with ether. The ether extract (B) was faintly yellow. This acidified mother liquor was then extracted with ethyl acetate thrice.

Treatment of the portion (B).—The ether-extract was evaporated whereby a yellowish residue was obtained mixed with some white crystals. This was first extracted with hot benzene. The ether-extract was much greater in quantity than that in the case of peat humic acid. The benzene extract on evaporation gave a yellowish white residue which was dissolved in cold water. The clear greenish filtrate on slow evaporation in a vacuum desiccator gave a gummy substance which was soluble in water and on drying melted at 139°. This may be veratroylformic acid. The portion which was insoluble in cold water was dissolved in hot water and the hot solution on cooling gave white crystals of veratric acid (m.p. 178°), more of which was obtained on concentration of the mother-liquor in vacuum. The last fraction from the evaporated solution melted at 143°.

Treatment of the portion (C).—The ethyl acetate fraction when evaporated gave a reddish brown residue. Unlike the former case hot benzene could extract nothing from the residue. The acetone extract of the residue gave a gummy substance on concentration and precipitation with acetonitrile as before.

Treatment of the portion (A).—The white amorphous mass obtained after acidifying the alkaline filtrate to congo red from the oxidised humic acid was washed with water. This was also insoluble in benzene and ether but soluble in acetone. The acetone extract on evaporation gave a yellowish amorphous mass which was treated with sufficient hot water. The hot solution on cooling gave a white powdery substance which was washed with water and dried in a desiccator. This substance when heated in a sealed tube decomposed at 105° and was strongly acidic in nature.

Oxidation of Soil and Peat Humic Acids by Chlorine Dioxide Solution of different Concentrations.—Different lots of humic acids were treated with chlorine dioxide solution of different concentrations for different intervals of time. The best result was found when for 1 g. of the acid 25 c. c. of 3% chlorine dioxide solution were used and the mixture kept for 24 hours at the room temperature in the dark, 5 g. of humic acids being taken in each operation. After keeping the humic acid in chlorine dioxide solution for 24 hours the insoluble portion was filtered off, washed thoroughly and then dried at 80°. The colour of the residue was light brown. Any increase either in the concentration of the solution or in the time disrupts the acid more vigorously. The filtrate was examined in the following manner :—

(a) A portion was evaporated to dryness. The dry contents were then extracted with ether, ethyl acetate and water successively. All the extracts were strongly acidic. The amount of water extract was greatest of all. After neutralisation with ammonia calcium chloride solution was added and the insoluble white calcium salt was treated with dilute sulphuric acid, warmed and treated with permanganate solution. The colour rapidly disappeared indicating the presence of oxalic acid.

(b) Another portion of the filtrate was subjected to steam distillation. A peculiar odour like that of butyric acid came out from the distillate.

(i) About 5 c. c. of the distillate were mixed with hydrogen peroxide solution (5 c. c.) and ferrous ammonium sulphate solution (1 c. c., 5 g. of ferrous ammonium sulphate and 10 c. c. of 40% sulphuric acid solution.). The mixture was heated at 70° for 5 minutes, treated with 6 to 7 drops of sodium hydroxide solution, cooled and filtered and 5 c. c. of the filtrate were mixed with 3 drops of alkali solution and 3 drops of 5% sodium nitroprusside solution and a slight excess of acetic acid. A red colouration developed showing the presence of butyric acid in the distillate.

(ii) A portion of the steam-distillate was treated with a solution containing cupric chloride bihydrate in *N*-hydrochloric acid and shaken with chloroform. On standing a slight red colour developed in the chloroform layer.

The above tests were confirmed by a blank experiment with fresh and very dilute butyric acid solution.